
Improving English Vocabulary through Picture Games at the Elementary School

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Abstract

The objective of the study was to enhance English vocabulary acquisition in elementary school students by utilizing visual games. The study aimed to assess the influence of utilizing graphic games on enhancing comprehension and memory of English vocabulary among elementary school students. Data is gathered via vocabulary assessments conducted before to and during the integration of the visual game, as well as through observations of student reactions during educational tasks. Data analysis employs both descriptive and inferential statistical methodologies. The research findings are anticipated to enhance the development of efficacious pedagogical approaches for enhancing English vocabulary acquisition in elementary school.

Keywords: English Vocabulary, Picture Games, MI Tarbiyatul Muhtadain

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Introduction

English is an international language that is often used by many people to interact with or communicate with other people in various parts of the world (Rao, 2019). One of the foreign languages most widely used to interact with other people is English (Lestari & Wahyudin, 2020). English is the language that has the most speakers, also known as Lingua Franca (Kirkpatrick & Schaller-Schwane, 2022). Acquiring proficiency in the English language is an exceedingly crucial endeavor. Given the current state of our modern society and the intense level of competition, it is widely assumed that individuals possess not only a high level of education but also specialized abilities, sometimes referred to as "skills." Fluency in English is considered a crucial talent in today's world. In order to effectively communicate on a global scale, it is essential to actively acquire proficiency in English, encompassing both oral and writing skills. According to Ki Hajar Dewantara Education, education is a guide in the life of children's growth (Bustomi et al., 2022), meaning that education guides all the natural strengths that exist in children (Frank et al., 2021), so that they, as humans and as members of society, can achieve the highest safety and happiness. Education is an activity in the form of learning, knowledge, and skills that occurs in the school room in order to develop

oneself and can produce changes in attitudes so that they become better. As we know, we have undergone various educations in the school environment, starting from early childhood education programs (PAUD), elementary school, middle school, high school, and undergraduate education. To increase student effectiveness, game-based learning media are used here. Children have an amazing ability to absorb language through play and other activities that they find enjoyable (Sahlberg & Doyle, 2019). So from the explanations above, we can use media that as an interesting to children in the form of games, videos, pictures, and others that can make students not easily feel bored when learning, because when the teacher provides media that can make students interested, then the students will be more active in studying it. The definition of media in the teaching and learning process tends to be interpreted as graphic (Burbules et al., 2020), photographic, or electronic tools to capture, process, and reconstruct visual or verbal information (Haris Budiman et al., 2016). Media are people, materials, or events that create conditions that enable students to acquire knowledge, skills, or attitudes (Aslan et al., 2020). The various types of media in learning can be visual media, audio media, and audio-visual media (Sarwinda et al., 2020). So here we can use media that can make students interested in learning, whether in the form of game-based learning media or others.

Game-based learning media is an educational approach that use games to facilitate learning and enhance students' engagement (Adipat et al., 2021). Its purpose is to cultivate students' interest in learning, preventing them from experiencing boredom during both in-class and out-of-class learning activities (Dewaele & Li, 2021). The researcher employed picture activities and discussions as pedagogical strategies to enhance the vocabulary of the children in this study. Due to their lack of interest in learning English, the researcher instructed them through picture activities and discussions. Following this, we assess their comprehension of the material by determining what they have learned through guessing the picture. We can determine who understands and who does not through discussions; if we already know everything, it is simple to provide them with guidance, allowing them to study diligently.

Skill can be defined as the capacity to apply logic, imagination, and thought to accomplish, modify, or transform something into something more significant, thereby generating value from the acquired knowledge. The abilities of MI students in grades 2 through 5 Tarbiyatul Mubtadiin exhibit subpar speaking and listening abilities due to their failure to prioritize listening during study time. Consequently, their listening skills are deficient. Similarly, their speaking proficiency is compromised as a result of insufficient

reading and study. There are multiple contributing factors to this condition, including challenges in verbal expression both inside and outside the classroom, such as difficulty generating ideas, and confusion regarding the correct usage of grammatically correct sentences. The present tense is frequently employed to describe events that occurred in the past. As a consequence, their lack of motivation diminishes their engagement in the instructional and learning processes. Additionally, they lack the self-assurance necessary to practice English in front of the class. Because they did not practice with their peers, this occurred. Students' ability to engage in extensive communication during the speaking class is one indicator of the class's success, as demonstrated.

The learning media consists of a bicycle, a blackboard, and detailed explanations and writings on the blackboard (Hafiz & Anisa, 2022). Since projectors and laptops are not available at school, the information written on the blackboard in front of the students and provide careful explanations to ensure they comprehend the lesson (Rido, 2020). Instructional media are essential for educators to cultivate greater student enthusiasm for learning (Agung et al., 2020). One of the methods or instruments utilized in the teaching and learning process is learning media. This is carried out in order to foster learning patterns that contribute to the efficacy of the teaching and learning process, thereby ensuring that instructional and learning endeavors successfully accomplish the intended objectives. An extensive variety of learning media is available for use. Particularly in the current era, technology has become an integral part of numerous spheres, including education. The purpose of educational media is to pique students' interest in the presented material.

There five previous relevance researches which examine teaching vocabulary through picture games. The first research was arranged by (Silalahi, 2019) with entitled "Improving Student's Interest in Learning English by Using Games." Second, employed by (Octaberlina & Anggarini, 2020) with entitled "Teaching Vocabulary through Picture Cards in Islamic Elementary School: A Case Study in Nida Suska School, Thailand". Third, was conducted by (Shabaneh, 2019) with entitled "The Effect of Games on Vocabulary Retention". Fourth, (Andreani & Ying, 2019) with entitled "PowPow Interactive Game in Supporting English Vocabulary Learning for Elementary Students". Fifth, (Jassim & Dzakiria, 2019) with entitled "A Literature Review on the Impact of Games on Learning English Vocabulary to Children".

A few researchers focused on improving the student's vocabulary. There have been limited studies concerned on how to improve the student's vocabulary skill. Therefore, the objectives of this research are improving student's vocabulary skill through a media

especially with picture games.

Research Method

Research methods are routine procedures used to accomplish a task in a systematic fashion so as to facilitate the execution of an endeavor with the intention of attaining the designated objectives (Ahamad et al., 2022). This study is an example of classroom action research. Researchers and classroom instructors collaborate in the development of a course of action. This elucidates that data comprises all information (data) pertaining to every aspect of the research objective.

MI Tarbiyatul Mubtadiin is an elementary school located in a village far from the city, the school consists of 6 classes and in grade 3 there are 25 students, but this research will focus on grade 3. This research will also focus on several aspects, namely speaking ability and student singing in using English, and so that they can be active again in learning English and the class conditions at school so that they are not too busy by themselves.

The assessment tool utilized in this research investigation comprised examinations of student responses to the following: monitoring students' attitudes throughout the instructional and learning process; directing students to concentrate more on their coursework during self-directed learning activities; and supervising students to increase their level of concentration. More emphasis must be placed on providing guidance to students so they do not embarrass themselves in the pursuit of knowledge.

The scholastic environment at MI Tarbiyatul Mubtadiin, particularly in third grade, remains unfavorable as a result of students' inadequate understanding of English education. Students who comprehend the material will remain silent and attend to the lesson if they are able to do so. Conversely, those who struggle with learning, particularly English, will not listen and instead prefer to speak independently. We can therefore conclude that students' learning is contingent on the manner in which the instructor explains and selects an effective method so that they are able to comprehend the material without becoming fatigued while in class. An English-learning game-based learning approach that utilizes guessing images as media. In this method, I will display images pertaining to English vocabulary and then ask students to identify the images I have displayed, as well as the names of the images, while employing the English language.

This study makes use of both qualitative and quantitative descriptive data. Qualitative data pertains to information regarding the quality of the subject under investigation (Mays & Pope, 2020). Its quantity consists of non-numerical units of quality, such as "special,"

"good," "bad," "high," "low," and "medium," among others. Quantitative data consists primarily of numerical values (Ahmad et al., 2019). The provided data signifies a numerical assessment of the investigated object expressed in specific units, such as length, breadth, weight, volume, and so forth. In this investigation, the increase in children's English vocabulary constitutes the quantitative data. Techniques of Data Collection This information was collected regarding the English vocabulary of young children. The collecting of data for this investigation was conducted by:

1. Observation

Observation is a data collection technique by observing every ongoing event and recording it with an observation tool about things to be observed or researched (Pandey & Pandey, 2021). Data collection through observation was carried out by researchers, research to get a direct description of student learning activities in class. Observations made included observations about the process of learning English, student activity and mastery of children's English vocabulary after learning with a picture game and discussion approach.

2. Interviews and Discussions

Interviews and discussions may be perceived as a method of data collection through the utilization of spoken language, which may be conducted in person or via specific media platforms (De Villiers et al., 2022). Discussions and interviews were conducted subsequent to and in accordance with the findings derived from classroom observations and document analysis. Following the initial observations of learning activities, interviews and discussions were conducted to gather information on a variety of topics pertaining to the implementation of English vocabulary learning for young children. The identified problem has been derived from the observational interviews and document evaluations that have been conducted.

Data analysis was undertaken by researchers subsequent to the conclusion of the teaching and learning process. An evaluation of the benefits and drawbacks of the teaching and learning process in schools, the coherence of the use of learning devices or media, and a variety of issues pertaining to the teaching and learning process were the objectives of this data analysis. Furthermore, through this observation or research, it is anticipated that any preexisting issues in the teaching and learning process can be revised in order to identify solutions for each such issue. Furthermore, this evaluation aims to enhance the execution of learning or teaching and learning processes, i.e., to rectify any shortcomings in the outcomes.

By utilizing this observation to assess the instruction and learning process the following day, it is possible to ensure that it improves even further than the day before.

Finding and Discussion

This chapter provides an exposition of the research outcomes and an analysis of the research conducted using the data gathered throughout the inquiry. Prior to presenting the research findings, a comprehensive outline of the subject profile is provided in this section. While the subject description does not constitute mandatory data, it remains crucial to provide an account of the subject's English perception. As described in the preceding chapter, MI Tarbiyatul Mubtadiin pupils, particularly those in the third grade, struggle to speak English. The following communication difficulties have been investigated:

Prior to elaborating on the analysis of the results, it is important to specify that this investigation is a classroom action research project. The present study was executed utilizing Collaborative Strategic Speaking. This method is intended to enhance the speaking comprehension of students. Following this, students will reread the instructor's words in a single line. Utilizing the application, students must identify the images that the instructor has displayed in front of them and deduce or interpret the English text. This endeavors to comprehend students' words not only when they are spoken but also when they are written, keeping in mind that writing and pronouncing words are not identical.

The researchers delivered a presentation of the research findings, which were derived from observations of the subjects. Also extracted are details from the documentation. The research findings will be expounded upon in the subsequent description.

During practice, the instructor will draw a line or circle and then select one student at a time to estimate. Students will then provide the expression they hypothesize. Enhancing the learning experience through the implementation of learning media in the form of image games involving the arrangement and formation of a single word is beneficial. The intervention implemented for the control group was personally conducted by the researcher. This is accomplished through the implementation of standard teaching and learning procedures.

The effectiveness of employing image game media as an educational instrument to augment the speaking proficiencies of students. At each meeting, data pertaining to the learning process is gathered. In order to assess student development, each session concludes with an assignment and review segment. The researcher subsequently observed the learning outcomes of each meeting in order to characterize the results.

Student's Name	Student's Response			Reasons
	Brilliant	Very Good	Good	
Nasrul		✓		Excellent conversational proficiency for comprehending English
Itsar	✓			You may evaluate its conduciveness to this child's learning because it is exceptionally excellent.
Mu'is	✓			Students must adhere to the instructor's subject orders; doing so constitutes compliance with his directives.
Azam		✓		Excellent conversational proficiency for comprehending English
Habibi	✓			Children may evaluate it according to how conducive it is to this child's learning, as it is exceptionally excellent.
Ila			✓	Child is not conducive to learning and therefore cannot read well.
Aldi		✓		Good in terms of conversation for reading English
Nisa'	✓			Children may evaluate its conduciveness to this child's learning because it is exceptionally excellent.
Rotib			✓	Child is not conducive to learning and therefore cannot read well.
Amel		✓		Children are required to adhere to the subjects specified by the instructor, which constitutes

				compliance with his directives.
Syaiful				Children may evaluate it based on how conducive it is to this child's learning because it is exceptionally effective.
Ma'we			✓	Children is not conducive to learning and therefore cannot read well.
Sholeha	✓			Excellent conversational proficiency for comprehending English
Anis	✓			Excellent for reading English conversational proficiency because the child is extremely receptive to learning.
Ilham		✓		Children are required to adhere to the subjects specified by the technician, which constitutes compliance with his directives.

Conclusion

It is necessary to incorporate English usage into daily activities. Not only with regard to reading English, but also with regard to speaking English. In actuality, however, the learning activities undergo modifications as a result of the curriculum replacement, particularly in English subjects. What is the role of English application in the educational process? This issue necessitates a resolution. Media must be utilised in its implementation to aid instructors in the learning process. By creating media, students not only address problems associated with learning English, but also enhance their speaking abilities. It is expected that students will muster the courage to explain and communicate in English through the use of visual media.

Following the implementation of image media, the instructor will conclude the meeting by reviewing reference materials to determine whether or not image media can enhance or improve students' speaking abilities. The utilisation or non-utilization of media must make a distinction. The incorporation of media will enhance the engagement and learning

experience. As demonstrated by the findings of this research, students can now confidently articulate the pronunciation of common English words such as family members, occupations, animals, colours, and commonplace verbs. Furthermore, they are capable of not only pronouncing but also writing English words accurately.

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